

The New Year's Eve Effect: Analysis of the presence of pyrotechnic explosives related ions in the background using IC-ESI-MS second part

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List of abbreviations

NFI	Netherlands Forensic Institute
E&E	Explosion and Explosives
IC-ESI-MS	Ion Chromatography Electrospray Ionization Mass spectrometry
NYEE 1 st ed.	New Year's Eve Effect (first edition 2017-2018)
NYEE 2 nd ed.	New Year's Eve Effect (second edition 2018-2019)
LOD	Limit of detection
LOQ	Limit of quantification
ppm	Part per million
V	Voltage
kV	Kilo Voltage
L/Hr	Litre per hour
m/z	Mass/charge ratio
ES	Environmental Survey
μ S/cm	Micro Simmens per centimetre
mM	Milli molar
μ l	Micro Litre
ppb	Parts per billion
RT	Retention time
S/N	Signal to noise

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1 Abstract

New Year's Eve is a very popular annual event. Most people save up for this event to purchase consumer fireworks and wait to ignite the firework on the day itself. Some ions which are present in consumer fireworks are also present in the environment and could have an impact on the data interpretations of a case related sample. A previous study (1st ed. NYEE) has been done. Some ions on some objects decrease to their average concentration with a period of a few weeks [2]. The aim of this study is to carry out a second edition of the NYEE focused on the cations. Colleagues from the Explosives team of the NFI volunteered to take samples in December 2018 and on the 1st of January 2019. The samples were taken by swabbing an A5 surface of an object with an isopropanol swab. After the sample preparations the samples were analysed with a new state-of-the-art ACN-enhanced isocratic cation chromatography method, which is coupled to an electro spray ionization mass spectrometry (IC-ESI-MS). It is observed that in some samples cations like copper, urea, ammonium, sodium and potassium are present. Although not all concentration could be determined because they are either above or below the calibration curve. And urea has been identified, however it is not possible to quantify and to say what the origin is. It could be coming from the swabs used for swabbing [1]. The results are obtained under the conditions as present during this study. In conclusion it is possible to quantify few cations in a certain range of the concentrations.

Key words: Consumer fireworks, pyrotechnics, forensic analysis, ion chromatography, mass spectrometry, New Year's Eve Effect, cations.

2 Introduction

At the NFI the explosion and explosives (E&E) team developed a new method to analyse pre- and post-blast pyrotechnic fireworks and explosives. The new technic, the IC-ESI-MS, will be used to analyse inorganic explosives. Except for solving casework, the NFI also invests a lot in research and innovation. For example, with the help and resources of the NFI it is possible to carry out the PyroProf project which is led by Dr Carlos Martín Alberca and funded by the NFI as the European Union. The PyroProf project can be divided in smaller parts related to the main aim which is developing analytical tools for the chemical profiling of inorganic explosives see **Figure 1**.

Photo 1 The NFI building from outside

Figure 1 General objective of the PyroProf project. The two red circles resembles the parts the author has been involved in.

As seen in **figure 1**, the red circles resembles the parts where the author has been involved in. As part of the validation of the cation method, which is developed for the PyroProf project, several experiments have been done. For example, determining the linearity, the LOD's and LOQ's. The author has been doing research on the validation of the cation method and has applied this to another study, the NYEE-second edition.

Linearity of the cations

Each cation has its own linear range. To find out the advisable linearity of those cations an experiment must be carried out. When designing an experiment like this several issues rise. For example, what range of concentration should be used, what is the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) of those ions, what kind of sample should be analysed, how to process the data. The aim is to obtain as much as information as possible about the linear range of each ion. The outcome of this experiment can be used in the validation process of the IC-ESI-MS.

In **table 1** the 18 cations in black are the ones which can be quantified because they are also present in the standards. Yet the four remaining cations in red cannot be quantified but could be identified, if present. For the 18 cations (in black) the linearity has been determined. After finding out the ranges, the software can calculate the concentrations of the cations present in the unknown samples. For some cations there is a linear range and for some a quadratic range (explained in **chapter 4.1**).

Table 1 The 18 cations which can be quantified. Yet there are four other ions (highlighted in red) which could be identified but cannot be quantified.

Cations included in the validation	
Lithium	Cadmium
Sodium	Cesium
Potassium	Copper
Magnesium	Zinc
Strontium	Aluminium
Lead	Ethylammonium
Barium	Dicyandiamide
Manganese	Ammonium
Calcium	Cobalt
Iron	Gadolinium
Urea	Nickel

New Year's Eve Effect 2nd ed.

As said in the introduction the aim of the NYEE 2nd ed. is to study the effects of an event such as New Year's Eve on the presents of the cations and the concentration there in. Prior to this edition there was a first edition done by Jesse Verbunt and Dr Carlos Martín Alberca [2].

When designing a study such as this, several issues rise. For example, what is the linearity of those ions, what are the LOD's and LOQ's, how big should the dataset be, how to collect the samples, how to process the samples and how to process the data.

The first step is to decide the size of the dataset. The dataset in the first ed. was approx. 130 samples. For the second ed. a smaller dataset seemed more appropriate. The dataset consists of 64 samples divided evenly over two sets. One set for the samples that were taken before NYEE and the other set was for the samples after NYEE. The volunteers were supposed to take samples before the 14th of December 2018 (for the before set). And then again on the 1st of January 2019 samples were taken by the volunteers as well. The volunteers took samples just as it was done in the first edition, using sample kits see **Figure 2** [2].

Figure 2 General photo of a sample kit which is used for taking samples. 1) the sample kit: 2) Form: 3) A5 frame: 4) sample bag.

In **figure 2 & 3** the requirements are visible for taking one sample. A: gloves; B: Frame, this frame can be placed over the object and then within the frame the surface can be swabbed; C: Isopropanol swabs (Braun B.) each object should be swabbed trice at different heights, D: Clamps: these are meant to hold the swab so it is not necessary to hold the swab with the gloves because gloves could cause contaminations, E: Jar: after the swab is taken from the object the swab is placed in the jar, F: Barcodes: after the swab is put in the jar the barcode is stuck on the jar; G Sample bag: Eventually the jar containing the swab is placed back in the sampling bag which is kept back in the sample kit; H: Form, the volunteer should fill in this form and give all the information required.

- A: Gloves
- B: Frame
- C: Isopropanol swabs
- D: Clamps
- E: Jar
- F: Barcode
- G: Sample bag
- H: Form

Figure 3 Requirements to take one sample (see the letters for the descriptions). A) gloves: B) frame: C) isopropanol swabs: D) clamps: E) jar: F) barcodes: G) sample bag: H) form.

The aim

In this document several aspects such as finding out the linearity of the 18 cations and the New Year's Eve Effect will be described. The aim is to find the linearity for each cation and to study the effect of fireworks in the environment before and after an event such as NYEE.

3 Theoretical framework

3.1 New Year's Eve Effect first edition

The first edition focused on the presence of anions in the background. The dataset contained 130 samples taken over a period. There were reference samples taken before NYE and the remaining samples were taken at 7 intervals in January 2018. It is observed that the presence and tendencies can be recognized for ions related to fireworks like chloride, nitrate, sulphate, thiocyanate, chlorate and perchlorate.

The ion chromatograph mass spectrometer (IC-MS) can be used for quantification of cations and anions. The NFI will use this instrument for future casework. The cation method is specific for 18 cations but can detect more cations if the full scans are enclosed in the method.

3.2 Specifications instrument & Method

The IC-ESI-MS (**Figure 4**) has a single quadrupole and is a very sensitive instrument. The IC separates compounds and the MS filters on the different masses of the ions. Some cation have several species which are analysed and could be related to the cations, see **chapter 3.5 cations**. The MS method has preprogrammed retention time windows for each ion of interest. These windows are based on the retention time of the ions with plus/minus a minute. Because the retention time windows are pre-programmed the ions should elute within this window otherwise there will be no peak visible in the chromatograms.

Figure 4 The IC-ESI-MS with an auto sampler

The IC will be used in isocratic mode at a constant flow of 1 mL/min and column temperature of 30°C. Right after switching on the method, the eluent will be pumped with a high-pressure pump at 0.8 mL/min during a minimum of 10 min. This step is required to equilibrate the system. Then, when the pressure is around 12.1, the flow rate must be increased up to 1 mL/min during a minimum of 5 min. After this, the column is equilibrated and is ready to use. See specification of the instrument and method in **table 2**.

The MS instrument will be operated in positive (ESI+) mode. Specific masses in the range 18.00 to 250.00 m/z will be monitored by selected ion recording (SIR) mode, at different cone voltages.

All data acquisition will be performed using MagIC Net Professional version 3.1. software from Metrohm and TargetLynx & MassLynx software's from Waters.

Table 2 Specification of the IC-ESI-MS used for the analysis of the cations.

IC-ESI-MS	Eluent:	4,9mM Oxalic acid + 25% Acetonitrile
	Flow:	1 ml/min
	Pressure:	14,7 MPa
	Column temperature:	30 °C
	Method	Isocratic
	Running time:	26 min
	Desolvation gas:	1200L/Hr
	Desolvation temperature:	350°C
	Capillary Voltage:	1kV
	Column:	cation-exchange column (250 x 4.0 mm)
	Sample loop:	20 µl

3.3 Materials

- Salts of each cation
- Acetonitrile from Biosolve UPLC pure
- Ultrapure water
- Oxalic acid form Sigma Aldrich
- Ethanol

3.4 Other requirements

- Sample kits (See **figure 2 & 3**)
- 10 ml syringes + 0,45 µm filters

3.5 Cations

In **table 3** all cations are shown which can be validated. In the column *species measured* the combinations of the molecules are given. Next column shows the masses which are analysed. One of these masses is the quantification trace. Meaning that, that mass is being used in the TargetLynx software to quantify. LOD and LOQ were determined as part of the validation of the cation method. LOD values are the values when the signal to noise (S/N) is minimum 3 and when a peak is visible. The LOQ values are at least 10 times the S/N. The values shown in the column LOD and LOQ's are given in ppb. Only after determining the LOD and LOQ's it can be decided how broad the range of the calibration curve should be.

Table 3 With the LOD's and LOQ's of 18 cations of interest. In this table most linearity of the cations are shown quadratic. This is because the range is quadratic when analysing standards up to 15 ppm. Also, whether the linearity is linear, or quadratic it has been programmed in the TargetLynx method.

Analyte and ionic formula*	Species measured	m/z	Cone voltage (v)	LOD and LOQ (µg/L)		Linearity (R ²)
				Instrument	Method	
Lithium – Li ⁺	[2ACN+Li] ⁺	89	10	0.5 / 0.6	0.75 / 0.8	quadratic
	[ACN+H ₂ O+Li] ⁺	66	30			
	[2ACN+2H ₂ O-H+2Li] ⁺	131	10			
Sodium – Na ⁺	[Na] ⁺	23	75 / 140	0.9 / 1.1	1000 / 1050	quadratic
	[ACN+ Na] ⁺	64	10			

Potassium – K ⁺	[K] ⁺	39	75 / 90	0.5 / 0.8	800 / 850	quadratic
Cesium – Cs ⁺	[Cs] ⁺	133	80	2.5 / 4	10 / 15	quadratic
Ammonium – NH ₄ ⁺	[NH ₄] ⁺	18	10 / 30 / 50	250 / 350	250 / 350	quadratic
Ethylammonium – C ₂ H ₈ N ⁺	[C ₂ H ₇ N+H] ⁺	46	10 / 30	30 / 40	160 / 200	quadratic
	[ACN-C ₂ H ₇ N] ⁺	86	10			
Dicyandiamide – C ₂ H ₄ N ₄ ⁺	[C ₂ H ₄ N ₄ +H] ⁺	85	10	12 / 15	18 / 24	quadratic
	[C ₂ H ₄ N ₄ -NH ₃] ⁺	68	30			
	[ACN+C ₂ H ₄ N ₄ +H] ⁺	126	10			
Magnesium – Mg ²⁺	[2ACN+5H ₂ O-H+Mg] ⁺	195	10	5 / 15	7.5 / 15	quadratic
	[Mg ₂] ²⁺	24	90			
	[4H ₂ O-H+Mg] ⁺	95	10			
	[2ACN+OH+Mg] ⁺	123	50			
	[3ACN+5H ₂ O-H+Mg] ⁺	236	10			
Calcium – Ca ²⁺	[2ACN+H ₂ O+Ca] ²⁺	70	30	50 / 60	300 / 400	linear
	[2ACN+2H ₂ O+Ca] ²⁺	79	30			
	[2ACN+3H ₂ O+Ca] ²⁺	88	30			
Strontium – Sr ²⁺	[H ₂ O-H+Sr] ⁺	105	140	80 / 200	320 / 500	quadratic
	[Sr ₂] ²⁺	87 and 88	140			
	[Sr] ²⁺	44	140			
Barium – Ba ²⁺	[Ba] ²⁺	69	70 / 140	600 / 800	1000 / 2000	quadratic
	[ACN-H+Ba] ²⁺ /[ACN+Ba] ²⁺	89.5	90			
	[H ₂ O-H+Ba] ⁺	155	90 / 70			
Manganese – Mn ²⁺	[2ACN+ 5H ₂ O-H+Mn] ⁺	226	30	25 / 37	150 / 200	quadratic
	[H ₂ O-H+Mn] ⁺	71	30			
	[ACN+ H ₂ O-H+Mn] ⁺	113	70			
Cobalt – Co ²⁺	[Co ₂] ²⁺	59	140	12 / 50	30 / 50	quadratic
	[4ACN+Co ₂] ²⁺	141	150			

Copper – Cu ²⁺	[Cu ₂] ²⁺	63	140	75 / 120	300 / 500	quadratic
		65	90			
Zinc – Zn ²⁺	[ACN+ 5H ₂ O-H+ ⁶⁴ Zn] ⁺	194	30	250 / 300	600 / 1000	quadratic
	[ACN+ H ₂ O-H+ ⁶⁴ Zn] ⁺	122	70			
	[ACN+ H ₂ O-H+ ⁶⁶ Zn] ⁺	124	70			
	[ACN+ H ₂ O-H+ ⁶⁸ Zn] ⁺	126	70			
Cadmium – Cd ²⁺	[¹¹² Cd ₂] ²⁺	112	140	275 / 375	500 / 800	quadratic
	[¹¹⁴ Cd ₂] ²⁺	114	140			
Aluminium – Al ³⁺	[2H ₂ O-2H+Al] ⁺	61	70 / 80	80 / 200	400 / 600	quadratic
	[3H ₂ O-2H+Al] ⁺	79	70 / 80			
Lead – Pb ²⁺	[²⁰⁸ Pb ₂] ²⁺	208	140	400 / 700	600 / 1000	quadratic
	[H ₂ O-H+ ²⁰⁶ Pb] ⁺	223	70 / 50			
	[H ₂ O-H+ ²⁰⁸ Pb] ⁺	225	70			

3.6 Database used for the NYEE 2nd ed.

As the sample kits contained each four different barcodes and these kits were distributed it was necessary to keep track of everything. For this reason, a database was built. This database is a refined version of the previous database which was created by Jesse Verbunt for the Environmental Survey (ES) which is also part of the PyroProf project.

Kit ID	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Distribution	Return
0113	ZRW2EJQA	KBAZBGEV	HU87JMWT	D25S39XV	Jacinta Jansen before 14-12-18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0116	TS17JFA3	KLMTU119	MRISUSNF	SSNSFMIR	Jacinta Jansen 01-01-19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0119	YTFPVDTE	PSTRPLBS	PPKRKEUB	SKCNCP7X	Annemieke van Hulsbergen before 14-12-18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0131	NRFKWSE6	BVVXAS6Q	WTL3NR2C	RQFLR65D	Annemieke van Hulsbergen 01-01-19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0133	NJNCL48P	WEPYTTJ5	YKFKPCAW	X3MKJE55	Eric Kok before 14-12-18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0134	CYS579PV	MRWXRAPC	AEP4Z3E2	QJRYWZTE	Eric Kok 01-01-19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0135	3YD4F3YV	TPR9BR4W	Q24WUCJH	ZAVXA61U	Shari Allers Gouda before 14-12-18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0142	PRHGYSMG	P9AHG8MQ	KKCFZDZH	7UP9EWE5E	Shari Allers Gouda 01-01-19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0143	VXXJBNEY	MSWG4ENU	TH7VAFBH	2UBDERS3	Shari Allers Roermond before 14-12-18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0145	TSSCFKSM	PH7GHPYH	SDPHTYRQ	AUJUYFFE	Shari Allers Roermond 01-01-19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0166	2TBMVCMK	KCSWGJDZ	PBMSPUXQ	R4XQPSQB	Shanaya Soeknandan before 14-12-18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0167	AUVS2K2K	SAK35LOV	ZQGKF2TP	SUUMP5B9	Shanaya Soeknandan 01-01-19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0176	UPXE8YTL	622XB2UT	Q4GSBSLV	H9KPATYV		<input type="checkbox"/>
0211	GCEMWLB3	NB26PC6H	EHCFTZEK	HSKGGSDG		<input type="checkbox"/>
0212	H314YWA8	CGNK9XLN	RXUXE2QC	K9CZYXUB	Chris before 14-12-2018	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0213	GWDQYL4A	DCSYRA5H	DPXKY7P7M	UTSFRUHF	Chris 01-01-2019	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0215	WHA6ZHYE	LHYXACMT	PRSNCC9U	RNALTRHP	Felix Amsterdam before 14 dec	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0217	7NJZ9DUX	GDXLGCTY	NN6J8GS2	F5XE4N6U	Felix Amsterdam	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
0218	STDJ9DVV	MVHDKYQA	MB4V55FP	FTZ2UUNT		<input type="checkbox"/>
0220	QYBQ7E24	NN4J7A3U	QRK69GN6	MEDCTUXZ		<input type="checkbox"/>
082	Q7PFQVGP	DQVBFNDE	VFDQFRAG	VWRZCUNB		<input type="checkbox"/>

These are the name of the sample kits.

Names of the volunteers and the dates for which set the sample kit was meant.

Figure 5 Database of the NYEE 2nd ed. In this section of database all record are kept about each sample kit, distributors, barcodes the kit contained and whether it has returned to the author or not.

PyroProf Project sample tracking

Rack ID: AFTERNYEE | Room/Lab: IC Lab (F3.19) | Storage: Freezer (F3.19 TT02_...)

Status: Analysis | Remarks: FBAFTER=Fridge Blank in the after NYEE bag

Sample prep by: Shanaya

Analysis by: | Data and analysis checks: Anions Cations Data (IC) GIS input Sign off CMA

Preparation date: 27-2-2019

Samples in rack: AFTERNYEE

A1	GWDQYL4A	B1	MRISUSNF	C1	SUUMP5B9	D1	CYS579PV
A2	SSNSFMIR	B2	TSSCFKSM	C2	TS17JFA3	D2	AEP4Z3E2
A3	AUJUYFFE	B3	7UP9EWE5E	C3	DCSYRA5H	D3	AUVS2K2K
A4	BVVXAS6Q	B4	RQFLR65D	C4	P9AHG8MQ	D4	UTSFRUHF
A5	NRFKWSE6	B5	PRHGYSMG	C5	GDXLGCTY	D5	
A6	KLMTU119	B6	SDPHTYRQ	C6	DPXKY7P7M	D6	
A7	PH7GHPYH	B7	ZQGKF2TP	C7	TB22FEB19	D7	
A8	7NJZ9DUX	B8	MRWXRAPC	C8	FBAFTER	D8	
A9	QJRYWZTE	B9	KKCFZDZH	C9	SAK35LOV	D9	
A10	F5XE4N6U	B10	WTL3NR2C	C10	NN6J8GS2	D10	

Sign for sample preparation: Shanaya | Sign for analysis: | 6-6-2019 9:16:32

Figure 6 Database NYEE 2nd ed. This form was designed to keep record of the samples. For each step in the process from extracted to data processed the samples needed to be scanned again.

3.7 Extracts

After the sample were collected and returned to the NFI (to the author) the samples were stored in a fridge until the time to extract them. While storing the samples in big plastic bags, a blank is also considered. Just to rule out any cross contamination in the bag. When time is ready the extracts were made in a laboratory room according to the NFI SOP 161501 [1]. See below the important steps of the extraction method described briefly:

- Clean the working place proper with ethanol and Ultrapure water before starting
- Take a swab from the table and code as a table blank.
- Then place three sheets on the working area
- Then take out the jars from the plastic bags and organize as to wish
- Pipette 10 ml of Ultrapure water into the jars
- Ultrasoon the jars for 10 min
- Take out the jars after the 10 min and extract as follow:
 - Suck all the liquid trough the swab using a plastic syringe
 - Place a 0,45 μm filter on the syringe and save the filtrate into a 15 ml falcon tube
- Register all sample with the correct status of the process in the database.
- Store the extracts in the freezer (-20°C.)

Analyse the samples when possible. When analysing few preparations need to be done. For example, the samples need to defrost, and eluent should be made. The eluent for this method consists of 25% Acetonitrile with 4,9mM Oxalic Acid filled with Ultrapure water.

3.8 Analysis

When analysing the extract also blanks (ultrapure water) and standards should be analysed as well. The most logical order of analysing is to start with a blank and then a standard of 1 ppm's to check if the eluent is correct. If the eluent is not correct then the conductivity can differ a lot from the standard value (666,6 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). Also, the ion will not elute within the programmed retention time window. After the standard, checks out to be good the sequence can be started. First the calibration standards from low to high concentration will be analysed. Then a blank, to prevent carryover from standard to unknown sample, and then the unknown samples can be analysed. After each 5 samples a reference standard of 1ppm and a blank is included in the sequence.

Table 4 The standards used for the calibration curves. These standards consist of 18 cations at different concentrations.

Standard	Concentration in ppm
1	0
2	0,2
3	0,4
4	0,8
5	1
6	2
7	4
8	8
9	10

4 Results & interpretation

After the analysis, the results were interpreted using the TargetLynx software. TargetLynx is a program which shows all the obtained data of each analysis. Also, if standards are included, this program can calculate the concentration of the unknown samples. All peaks need to be reviewed before collecting the data.

4.1 Processing data: Linearity

In **table 5** the outcome of the linearity experiment is shown. For this experiment calibration standards with a broad range from 0 to 10 ppm was analysed. The standards were prepared in volumetric flasks. After the analysis, the results of this experiment have been studied. While studying the results some cations had a linear range up to 10 ppm. The hypothesis was that the range would go up to 15 ppm for some cations. To confirm the theory if the range of the linearity was beyond 10 ppm, two higher standards have been studied. These two higher standards, 12,5 ppm and 15 ppm, contained 18 cations and were meant for a different experiment.

The aim was to obtain the best linear and quadratic ranges for the cations. To obtain the best results the R^2 was very important. The closer the R^2 value was to 1, the better. For some cations the linear range is narrow but if looked to the quadratic range, this range can go up to one or two standards higher. In **figure 7** and **figure 8** two examples are given of a linear and a quadratic calibration curve.

Table 5 The advisable linear and quadratic ranges of the 18 cations.

Cation	Linear range	Quadratic range
Lithium	0 – 0,8 ppm	0 – 1 ppm
Sodium	0 – 2 ppm	0 – 4 ppm
Potassium	0 – 4 ppm	0 – 6 ppm
Magnesium	0 – 2 ppm	0 – 6 ppm
Strontium	0 – 10 ppm	0 – 15 ppm
Lead	0 – 10 ppm	0 – 12,5 ppm
Barium	0 – 10 ppm	0,4 – 15 ppm
Manganese	0 – 4 ppm	0 – 8 ppm
Calcium	0 – 10 ppm	0 – 15 ppm
Cobalt	0 – 10 ppm	0 – 12,5 ppm
Cadmium	0 – 10 ppm	0 – 12,5 ppm
Cesium	0 – 10 ppm	0 – 15 ppm
Copper	0 – 10 ppm	0 – 12,5 ppm
Zinc	0 – 1 ppm	0 – 2 ppm
Aluminium	0 – 8 ppm	0 – 15 ppm
Ethylammonium	0 – 0,8 ppm	0 – 4 ppm
Dicyandiamide	0 – 4 ppm	0 – 8 ppm
Ammonium	0 – 1 ppm	0 – 1 ppm

Compound name: Strontium
Coefficient of Determination: $R^2 = 0.999071$
Calibration curve: $-5327.74 * x^2 + 423691 * x + -8279.69$
Response type: External Std, Area
Curve type: 2nd Order, Origin: Exclude, Weighting: $1/x$, Axis trans: None

Figure 7 Linear calibration curve of Strontium with a range from 0-10ppm.

Compound name: Ammonium
Coefficient of Determination: $R^2 = 0.999992$
Calibration curve: $-21548.5 * x^2 + 40811.2 * x + -6326.63$
Response type: External Std, Area
Curve type: 2nd Order, Origin: Exclude, Weighting: $1/x$, Axis trans: None

Figure 8 Quadratic calibration curve of Ammonium with a range from 0-1ppm.

4.2 Processing data: NYEE 2nd ed.

4.2.1 Visuals of the objects

The volunteers took pictures of the object they swabbed. **Figure 9** is a traffic sign, **figure 10** is nice composition of firework next to a plant pot and **figure 11** is a lamp post.

Figure 9 Traffic sign

Figure 10 Building material: plant pot

Figure 11 Lamp post

4.3 Processing data: Standard check

During the analysis of the unknown samples there were also 1 ppm 18 cations standards analysed. In **figure 12** an overlay is shown of five analysed standards. In this chromatogram all peaks are the same and no huge differences.

Figure 12 Overlay of five IC chromatogram of 5 standards 18 cations at 1ppm concentration.

There is a difference between a chromatogram of a standard 1ppm and an unknown sample. See in **figure 13** an example. The left chromatogram is of a 1ppm 18 cation and the right chromatogram is of an unknown sample. Note that only a few out of the 18 cations are shown. When a peak is not present only noise is visible like for barium. Because there is a lot of data that needs to be processed it is easier to use TargetLynx.

Figure 13 Example of few cations in a MS chromatogram in MassLynx. Left: chromatogram of a 1ppm 18 cation standard. Right: chromatogram of an unknown sample.

4.4 Processing data: TargetLynx & IC

After the analysis the data have been studied. Each peak had to be reviewed because in some situations the software does either not recognize the peak or it recognizes a peak which cannot be considered as a peak. A requirement is that the S/N should be at least 3 or higher if considered as a peak. Also, in all channels of the cation a peak should be visible. To quantify a peak, the requirement is that the S/N should be 10 times higher.

One of the ions found in most of the samples was copper, see **figure 14**. In both channels a clear peak is visible.

Figure 14 Bottom right: chromatogram of copper with both channels. Bottom left: the calibration curve shown with a range from 0-10ppm. Top: list of all analysis and the data of each analysis.

4.5 Processing data: Overview in excel

Because of the huge amount of data, the author chose to make an overview in excel. In this sheet (see **figure 15**) all information is present from component, object type, file name, sample ID, area, retention time (RT), signal to noise (S/N) and the concentration in ppm calculated by TargetLynx. Processing I excel makes it easier to sort on a specific group as is sorted on standard 0,2ppm in **figure 15**.

Component	Name	ID	Object type	Area	RT	S/N	ppm
Aluminum	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	103434	1.83	33	0,2
Ammonium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	970	4.24	3	0,2
Barium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	16927	20.49	1	0,2
Cadmium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	10997	8.73	6	0,2
Calcium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	84585	7.31	5	0,2
Cesium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	619989	8.61	315	0,2
Cobalt	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	115335	3.67	94	0,2
Copper	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	106334	2.11	13	0,2
Dicyandiamide	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	72835	2.82	400	0,2
Ethylammonium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	6273823	4.90	19	0,2
Lead	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	68751	16.41	11	0,2
Lithium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	6469624	3.02	4345	0,2
Magnesium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	62500	5.04	90	0,2
Manganese	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	28400	5.16	55	0,2
Potassium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	2143557	6.29	231	0,3
Sodium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	1626231	3.98	83	0,2
Strontium	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	76608	10.37	20	0,2
Urea	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard				
Zinc	20190305_08	Ijkljn-Standard 0.2ppm	Standard	7288	3.21	1	0,2

Figure 15 Overview data recovered. In this example all information is given of one standard 0,2ppm. from left to right: components, file name, sample ID, object type, area, retention time, signal to noise and concentration in ppm.

4.6 Processing data: Manually calculating the concentration with an quadratic equations

Because for some cations the software could not calculate the concentration automatically, the concentration have been calculated manually in excel. For example see **figures 16, 17 and 18**. In figure 16 a) the equation and the y are given. The question is to solve this equation to find x. This equation is solved the abc-formula. $x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$. After solving this x_1 and x_2 are known, with this information it is possible to create a table with several point to make eventually a mountain parabol (see **figure 18**)

	ax ²		bx		c	
f(x)=	-5571,83	+	435761	+	-14712,4	
y=	342461					
	c ₁		-14712,4			Fill in
	a		-5571,83			
	b		435761			
	c ₂ = c ₁ - y		-357173,4			
	D=b ² -4ac		181927211259,71			
	Nulpunten		1 of twee nulpunten			
	x1=		77,37944822			
	x2=		0,828429627			
	top					
	y=ax ² +bx+c					
	x		39,10393892			
	y		8519985,764			

Figure 16 The quadratic equations of strontium is shown.

tabel	
x	y
-5	-2675274,15
-4	-2189366,68
-3	-1714602,87
-2	-1250982,72
-1	-798506,23
0	-357173,4
0,124	-303224,7085
1	73015,77
2	492061,28
3	899963,13
4	1296721,32
5	1682335,85
10	3443253,6
15	4925579,85
20	6129314,6
25	7054457,85
26	7206055,52
28	7475819,88
30	7701009,6
40	8158338,6
50	7501301,6
60	5729898,6
70	2844129,6
78	-266829,12

Figure 17 After calculating the intersection with the x-axis a table is created with several points to form a parabol.

Figure 16 A parabol of strontium.

4.7 Processing data: Before vs After

In **table 6** a summary is given of the cations noticed in the samples while processing the data. Below the table in **figures 19 till 23** the results are shown in graphs.

Table 6 Summary of the cations present and those which are not present.

Cations found
Ammonium was found in a lot of samples, but the S/N was below 10 so it cannot be considered as a peak for quantification. However, ammonium was identified. In 3 samples from the before batch (wooden pole, Lamp post and window) there was ammonium found in a concentration above 1ppm. The actual concentration is not known because the areas of those samples were above the area of the highest standard.
Calcium was found in most samples, but the concentrations varied between 0,1 and 0,5 and the S/N was below 10 so those peaks cannot be quantified. See in figure 19 an overview of the calcium found in several samples.
Copper was found in most samples. See figure 20 .
Magnesium was found in a lot of samples. However, for some the S/N value was below the 10 so those cannot be considered as a peak. See figure 21 .
Sodium was found in all samples. However, in the samples before NYEE there was more sodium present. See figure 22
Potassium was found in all samples. See figure 23 .
Strontium was found in one sample. The concentration was approx. 0,8 ppm in before as in after sample. The S/N was in the before sample 33 and in the after sample 10.
Zinc is identified in the samples but cannot be quantified because the signal to noise is below 10.
Cations not found
Aluminium, Barium, Cadmium, Cesium, Cobalt, Lead, Dicyandiamide, Ethylammonium, Manganese and Urea Urea is present in the samples but cannot be quantified. As for this reason there is no graph.

Figure 19 Comparison of calcium in samples before vs after NYEE 2nd ed. The objects in which calcium was found are only shown. The other objects are not shown because they did not contain calcium at a concentration enough to quantify.

Figure 20 Comparison of copper in samples before vs after NYEE 2nd ed. The blue bars resemble the concentrations found before NYE. The green bars resemble the concentration found after NYE.

Figure 21 Comparison of magnesium in samples before vs after NYEE 2nd ed. The red bar resembles the concentration found before NYE and the purple bars the concentration found after NYE.

Figure 22 Comparison of sodium in samples before vs after NYEE 2nd ed. The red bars resemble the concentrations found before NYE while the purple bars resemble the concentrations found after NYE. Sodium shows a high presence in most samples. For this reason, makes it more difficult to trace its origin back.

Figure 23 Comparison of potassium in samples before vs after NYEE 2nd ed. The orange bars show the concentrations found before NYE while the light blue bars resemble the concentrations found after NYE.

5 Discussion

The concentration given in the graphs are based on a mean of the concentrations of that cation found. There were for some categories more samples taken. But it is not justified to say that the concentration given is the exact concentration. Some traces can come from the object itself and is probably not related to the firework.

At first a different method should have been used instead of the used one. The other method contained extra full scans, so the method could scan other present ion or masses which are not recorded in the program. Five additional full scan channels (i.e., MS scan mode) at different cone voltages (i.e., 10 V, 30 V, 50 V, 70 V and 90 V) might be set in continuum for scanning the entire spectrum (18.00 to 400.00 m/z) looking for ions produced by unknown compounds in matrices (e.g., interferences).

Urea peak is present in the unknown samples, but it could be related to the swab because it is known that the swabs from Braun B. contains traces of several cations, including Urea. The amount in those swabs has not been determined so far. However, there is a positive peak for urea, only the source is still unknown. Either the urea comes from the swab or from the object. It is not possible to quantify urea because the standard does not contain urea.

For the before as for the after batch each time fresh eluent has been prepared. There is no huge difference observed due to that.

For some ions the linearity turned out to be linear from 0-10ppm but in the method it was already programmed quadratic. Even after changing the method the formula in Target Lynx kept saying quadratic while it is linear. It is possible that TargetLynx saves the parameters at time of the analysis. For this reason, the author tried to calculate for some samples the concentration manually instead of using TargetLynx. Because the author tried doing this manually there could be a slight difference in concentration because TargetLynx calculates with all decimals that are not shown.

Some areas of the cations were above the highest standard so TargetLynx could not calculate the concentration. A solution would be to dilute the sample and analyse it again. After the analysis it is possible to calculate backwards to the concentration in the real samples.

The samples of the NYEE-first edition have been analysed for cations but the data processing is still going on. For this reason, only the results of the second edition have been discussed in this document.

6 Conclusion

There have been ions found in higher concentrations than in the before samples. However, these are not seen in the graphs clearly because the concentrations are above the highest concentration. So, there is an increase after NYE. Also, there are some ions which cannot be traced back to its origin. For example, urea is present in the swabs used but the amount is not known. Also, in a blank standard sodium and potassium were present but this is relatable to the use of glassware.

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8 Author

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10 Supplementary data

- Raw data before (Excel)
- Raw data after (Excel)
- Calculating concentration with quadratic equation (Excel)
- Raw data before & after (.xps)
- Sample photo's (.jpeg)
- Calibration curve of all cations before and after NYE (.xps)

For questions approach: Dr Carlos Martín Alberca

11 Appendix

Figure 24 Linear chromatogram of cesium in a 10ppm standard. Left: the calibration curve made by TargetLynx shows that cesium has a linear range up to 10ppm. Right: cesium peak.

